

METHODS FOR DETERMINING LEADERSHIP QUALITIES AND ABILITIES IN STUDENTS

Zaynobidinov J.

Fergana State University, Candidate of Psychological Sciences, Associate Professor

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11264998>

Abstract. *In this article, students have identified those who are capable of management, forming leadership qualities in the process of their activities. The group is empirically based on the qualities of leadership that are manifested in the educational process, which is the leading activity of students in the conditions, as well as in the conditions of mutual cooperation.*

Keywords: *intelligence, management, ability, "leader", "leader", "scientific management", X-theory, Y-theory.*

Introduction. The development of the ability to adapt to the innovations of the modern world, prepare the younger generation for the life of a constantly updated society and actively participate in the processes of improving it in accordance with the requirements of the time is an important professional task of the Educator of a higher educational institution. It is known that compulsory general secondary education in our Republic is strengthened by law. Such education can be obtained through general education schools, Lyceum gymnasiums, secondary vocational institutions and an extensive network of commercial schools.

Of the 4 people employed in the field of material production and services, one has a higher or secondary specialized education. As can be seen from the above data, the educational system in our republic is well established, which shows its positive effect on the development of the intellect to increase the mental capacity of students. The importance of higher education institutions is great in this. It is the sacred duty of each of us to teach young people in what way, to educate them, to grieve for them to become mature professionals of an independent country.

The management problem became one of the most pressing problems in the late 20th and early 21st centuries. This condition is characterized by an increased role of human factor in all social processes. In addition, in humans, personal qualities such as a passion for leadership from an early age, a tendency to strive for success in service positions also begin to manifest themselves. Such social psychological phenomena are primarily aimed at further improving the field of management, increasing its effectiveness. the influential role of this factor in issues such as labor productivity and improving human relations has made it relevant to the increased agenda.

For Uzbekistan, which is following the path of independent development, the issue of improving the management system of KHAM, the selection, training, skill development of executive personnel, the creation of conditions related to a higher level of their knowledge levels are becoming an important factor in development.

Psychology recognizes that when one sees people who are subjects of managerial activity, there are two categories. This is the concepts of "leader" and "leader". The first concept is more used to refer to a person who acts in a system of formal relations, whose main task is to exert on the person who exercises the authority of the organization before the state and society, while the leader is the product of informal relations within the community, directly responsible to the spiritual and psychological environment in the community. With the concept of a leader, there is a desire to harmonize the problems of the management system as a whole. True, there are also a

number of concepts related to management issues, such as "manager", "boss", "chef", but from this point of view, this phenomenon is carried out within the framework of leadership.

Literature analysis. If we look at the history of these phenomena, then the initiator of Applied work in the fields of management theory and practice is F. Taylor is. Later, this direction began to be called "scientific management". The founder of the ready-made new system of functional administration emphasizes that it is necessary to give great importance to quality management styles, disciplinary sanctions and a system of incentives. He recommended a differential system of Labor remuneration as the basis of motivation for labor in people, in a way that emphasized the particular role of stimulation.

One of his followers is D. Jilbert, on the other hand, put forward the idea of a condition for people to work well and efficiently, improving their jobs and the conditions there.

E., who promoted human relations as an important factor in the effective organization of production. Mayo had proven that the manager must first of all take into account that a person is satisfied with his professional and social condition. He noted: for the first time, that there could not be a clearly defined head-boy hierarchy in management, something that only negatively affects psychologismuchit in the team. Therefore, Ham he put forward the idea that individual stimulation should be replaced with gruppavoy, economy — with socio — psychological factors.

Mayo developed Management and developed a. Laykert defines the following 15 factors of good governance:

- from management styles there is such that the leader trust its employees;
 - who attracts the employee to an active cocktail, gruppavoy activity forms of motivation;
 - the type of communication that reaches everyone equally;
 - with the participation of all members and their opinions take care decisions;
- Goals set as a result of the general discussion of the team;
Decentralized form of control.

Among the theories devoted to management problems, De McGrory's "X" and "instructional theories require a special calling. While" Theory X "refers to the Administrative - Command-based principles of an approach to governance," theory of learning " is fundamentally different from it. The " X " approach relies on:

1. Adamng actually has no tolerance for labor, giving him to avoid work the tendency is strong.

2. From taking risks and responsibilities to an ordinary person escape is inherent, it is passive and resistant to controls.

3. A normal person does not need much, so if they leave him alone, he needs protection, safety. "in contrast, ¥ - theory is based on:

1. The physical and intellectual capabilities of a person it is natural for him to strive to spend, and for him it is as interesting as a cocktail activity or study.

2. Self — control and control in the process of human labor has the ability to.

3. Usually a person seeks to take responsibilities on his own and feels extirpated to show his talent.

4. What a person encourages to take responsibility for is it is a tendency to participate in general activities.

The need for creative work in many to take initiatives there is a craving, this thing I imple on management.

In the practical part of our discussion and results study, we initially used the methodology “do you have the ability to lead” on Guruh results analysis. This methodology was selected in 30 object examiners at the Faculty of nature and geography. There are people who wait for someone's support, guidance before carrying out each work. They are not used to independent movement on their own. In this methodology, we can find out to what extent the qualities of leadership in students are. This methodology consisted of 15 questions and was evaluated in three variants, with variants scoring 15, 5, 0. At the end of our investigation, the scores were calculated and separated by the scores of our testers. 12 of our testers were boys and 18 were girls. This is indicated in the percentage, while boys made up 40% and girls made up 60%. 15 of our testers collected results up to 120 points. 11 testers showed results up to 180 points, while 4 testers showed results up to 200 points. Showing this in percentages was 50% up to 120 points, 36.6% up to 180 points, and 13.3% up to 200 points.

Table 1

“Do you have the ability to control?” methodology analysis

No	F .I. Sh	Ballari	Results
1	Mamarasulov D	110	Below 120 points: you do not mind who is in control of yourself. Because, you are more inclined to be a great employee than a leader.
2	Ismoilova Z	110	
3	Mamataev A	80	
4	Hazratqulova. M	110	
5	Baxromova M	100	
6	Mahmudjonova G	105	
7	Tursunboyev M	115	
8	Yo’ldasheva M	90	
9	Bobobekova M	100	
10	Tolipova R	115	
11	Madatova M	60	
12	Abduxalilova I	90	
13	Ergasheva M	85	
14	Raxmonova M	105	
15	Ergasheva E	85	
16	Qo’ldashev M	135	You don't like someone ordering you a job. But you yourself do not want to command someone. So you're stuck between the two ways.
17	Soliyev A	140	
18	Nosirov U	125	
19	Akbarova H	145	
20	Saidova N	135	
21	Qobilov K	125	
22	Sunnatov F	130	
23	To’lanova R	155	
24	Maripova E	145	

25	Roziqov J	160	You are a person inclined to rule over others. If we are not mistaken, you are still in the leadership position
26	To'lanova A	135	
27	Yo'ldashev M	185	
28	Azizova B	195	
29	Jamolov O	190	
30	No'monov T	190	

Of these ten listed executive qualities, testers would have to be numbered in levels. Using this methodology, we learned what qualities a leader's personality should have. Comparing these results, the more points are reduced, the higher the quality of the leader goes to the first place. Of the adjectives, the most tested are those that put adjectives like knowledgeable, fair, with scores of 48-59.

In the results obtained according to the method of “determination of leadership qualities” conducted at the well, students are shown the qualities of leaders.

The quality of knowledge-the first level of our respondents who participated in the strike, it is clear that the leading person will have to be educated first of all. A knowledgeable person must be sufficiently aware of other spheres without knowing only his sphere, and only then can such a person be called a knowledgeable person. The results obtained in terms of cognitive quality are approximate. In this investigation, girls chose a more erudite quality compared to boys, 25% of girls put this quality in high positions, from which it is clear that girls think that the leader should be more erudite. Even in our analysis below, the quality of erudition has been put in high places by the testers.

The quality of knowledge-the first level of our respondents who participated in the strike, it is clear that the leading person will have to be educated first of all. A knowledgeable person must be sufficiently aware of other spheres without knowing only his sphere, and only then can such a person be called a knowledgeable person. The results obtained in terms of cognitive quality are approximate. In this investigation, girls chose a more erudite quality compared to boys, 25% of girls put this quality in high positions, from which it is clear that girls think that the leader should be more erudite. Even in our analysis below, the quality of erudition has been put in high places by the testers.

Fair quality-our respondents who participated in the strike came in second place in our strikes to put their fair quality on higher levels. A fair leader means that the employees are treated equally, if they make mistakes or make a fair hokum in their quarrels, and we enter into the abilities of the employees to be able to understand their circumstances.

Analysis of the results obtained on fair quality. In our investigation, it was found that 45% of this quality boys 55% girls placed in high positions it is clear that girls chose more than boys the leader should be fair to girls.

Organizational quality-this quality is considered one of the main qualities of the leader. Because the leading person should be the organizer of all work more than the employees. When planning leisure activities in the organization of events, all must have an organizer.

Results obtained in terms of organizational quality. Our respondents also put this quality at higher levels, but this quality is indicated in our study at the third level. The study found that 25.4% of girls placed higher and 30.6% of boys placed higher. This quality was placed more highly by the boys, from which it was determined that the quality of organization should be in the main places for the boys.

Orderly quality-this quality should be not only in the leader, but also in each individual. An orderly person can plan his work for life and have time for all. Where order is a discipline, there is always a high level of work productivity. And this should be exemplified by the leader himself showing the employees.

Analysis of the results obtained in order quality. The results of the study were 42.6% in girls and 33.8% in boys. From this it can be seen that the quality of the layout also put girls children in high places. In the opinion of the girl Boas, within the qualities of the leader, there should also be an orderly quality in the main places.

The quality of a serious leader - of course, being serious to a person increases respectability, and seriousness helps a person to approach each job with a deep thought. In this study, students determined the quality of seriousness in determining leadership qualities by placing them in fifth place.

Serious leader quality analysis. During our study, this quality was 36.5% in girls and 60.5% in boys. Inside our testers, we can see that the indicators for this quality in boys are high. The leader, according to the opinion of the children, became the idea that a person should be a serious person.

A lover of his profession – of course, every person should love the profession in which he operates, only then will he Rise and become a master of his profession.

Therefore, the leader will have to love his profession first of all. Such a leader will certainly be able to understand the employees of this profession and realize the difficulties of the profession. In our opinion, lovers of the profession are considered real selfless people.

Analysis of results on the quality of the professional lover. During our studies, we found out that the girl ate 65.7% in children, and 33.5% in children. From this it can be seen that the main girl children have put this quality in high places. They argue that it is difficult to be a good leader without loving his profession.

Interaction quality-this quality should be present not only in the leading person, but also in every person, because the main role is played when communicating with people. The Hushmomla leader will also be easy to gain respect among the employees. The quality of Hushmomla requires that people be treated with laughter to be sincere.

Interaction qualitative results analysis. One of the following qualities of our study was the quality of hushmomla in girls 55.4% in boys 45.6%. According to the testers, hushmomlalik insisted that it was one of the main qualities of the leader.

Cultured quality – in this quality, not only the leader, but also the appearance, gait, behavior and how each individual acts in public places all penetrate into these qualities. A civilized leader should also respect others with self-esteem. Then the real cultured leader is considered.

Analysis of the results of the cultured quality. Among our testers, 42.6% in girls were 58.4% in boys. Boys on this quality turned out to be high. It can be seen from this that the boys agreed in the opinion that the leading person should be madantatli. (Table 9. Diagram 8)

Loving quality-kindness is the sonority of the leader to his employees, they will always have to understand them and, if necessary, also help in their personal lives. The real leader is the one who thinks of his co-workers and the one who lives is the leader.

Analysis of affectionate adjectives. Among the testers, 25.9% of girls were 33.8% in boys. This quality set the lowest possible results among our testers, which means that the leader came to the idea that the person does not have to be highly affectionate during the work. (Table 10. Table 9).

Truthful quality-truthfulness serves to build mutual trust between people. Leader shaxda also constitutes the self-confidence between the employees and the leader. Therefore, the leader should definitely be truthful.

Analysis of the results obtained in terms of truthful quality. As the end of our study, it was 25.9% in girls and 30.8% in boys. Our testers of this quality put it in the last place, they came to hulosa that this quality of the leader is not important. From the analysis of the results, it was determined that the leader should be a strong person of psiologic knowledge.

In conclusion, it should be said that in conclusion we can say that in the development of the personality of the future leader, it will be necessary to organize trainings in students and train and educate them in their profession, making them resolute and ambitious in their work, in addition, among the listed leases, the following can be included:

1. Master of the leader to a realistic, scientifically predictable future;
2. The businessman, dexterity, resourcefulness of the monk.
3. The success of collective activity in expression in economic socio-cultural ideological soas.

REFERENCES

1. O‘zbekiston Respublikasining Oila kodeksi. – T.: «Adolat», 1998. – 302 b.
2. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Konstitutsiyasi –T: «O‘zbekiston», 2018.– 40 b.
3. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2019 yil 13 fevraldagi «2019-2025 yillarda O‘zbekiston Respublikasi aholisining ruhiy salomatligini muhofaza qilish xizmatini rivojlantirish kontseptsiyachini tadiqlash to‘g‘risida»gi PQ- 4190 - son qarori/Qonun hujjatlari ma’lumotlari milliy bazasi, 15.02.2019 y., 07/19/4190/2614-son.
4. Abdullayev Y.O Menejment. «Boshqarish nazariyasi va boshqalar asoslari». T. 1998 yil
5. Baratov SH.R “Mehnat jarayoni va ijtimoiy-ruhiy jihatlar/ Iqtisod va hisobot”. 1997 yil